

Extreme temperatures in Eastern United States likely influenced by both human-driven climate change and natural variability

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Press Summary (First Published 2024/06/25)

- Heatwaves similar to the Eastern US heatwave are up to 2 °C warmer than the warmest heatwaves previously observed in this area
- This was a somewhat uncommon event
- We mostly ascribe the high temperature in the Eastern US heatwave to human driven climate change and natural climate variability likely played a modest role

Event Description

From June 18th to June 23th the [Eastern United states experienced a severe heatwave](#).

Over 75 million people across the eastern U.S. were under heat warnings or advisories

as cities on the East Coast braced for record-breaking temperatures. Baltimore and

Philadelphia reached near 40°C, [while calendar-day records were broken across the](#)

[east](#). Philadelphia region faced dangerous conditions due to high humidity. New York

City health officials reported a 500% increase in heat-related emergency room visits.

Flooding has also been experienced in the mid-west, [with some regions experiencing](#)

[both extreme heat and flooding](#). In Iowa, a breached levy prompted evacuations in Rock

Valley, assisted by Sioux City Fire Rescue.

The *Surface Pressure Anomalies* reveal a strong positive anomaly over the Atlantic Coast of the United States. These conditions favor *Temperature Anomalies* up to +7°C. *Precipitation Data* show an absence of precipitation in the southern U.S. and large amounts of precipitation, reaching up to 20mm/day, in the northern U.S. and along the Canadian-U.S. border. *Windspeed data* show low to moderate winds, especially in coastal areas and the Great Lakes region.

24-Jun-2024 CNRS-IPSL (MSWX Data)

ClimaMeter for Eastern US Heatwave 19-Jun-2024 to 23-Jun-2024

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Surface Pressure Anomalies Temperature Anomalies

Precipitation Data

Windspeed Data

Surface Pressure Changes

Temperature Changes

Precipitation Changes

Windspeed Changes

Similar Past Events

Changes in Urban Areas

Climate and Data Background for the Analysis

Observations show that hot extremes, including heatwaves, have intensified in cities, aggravating air pollution events and limiting the functioning of key infrastructure (IPCC AR6 WGII SPM). We have high confidence that, in urban areas, the temperature increases associated with urbanization (the heat island effect) combined with more frequent hot extremes due to climate change will increase the severity of heatwaves (IPCC AR6 WGI SPM- Page 25). The IPCC reports highlight several key points about heatwaves in the US. Past observed trends are inconclusive for the Eastern North-America region (IPCC, AR6, WGI, Chapter 11), but future projections by all model ensembles show a high confidence of an increase of extreme heat events in these regions, with a high probability that such a signal will emerge from the natural variability in the next decades (IPCC. WGI, Chapter 12)

Heatwaves are significantly impacting the Eastern United States, particularly in urban areas. The [2018 US National Climate Assessment](#) has identified that southeastern USA is already experiencing more frequent and longer summer heatwaves and, by 2050, rising global temperatures are expected to mean that more cities in southeastern USA may experience extreme heat. This includes disadvantaged African American communities, who are more exposed and hence disproportionately experience the impacts of climate change.

Our analysis approach rests on looking for weather situations similar to those of the event of interest having been observed in the past. For this event we have medium-high

confidence in the robustness of our approach given the available climate data, as the event is somewhat unusual in the data record

ClimaMeter Analysis

We analyze here (see [Methodology](#) for more details) how events similar to the high temperature in the Eastern US heatwave changed in the present (2001–2023) compared to what they would have looked like if they had occurred in the past (1979–2001) in the region [90°E 68°E 32°N 50°N]. The *Surface Pressure Changes* show that similar events display significant changes (up to +1 hPa) in the present climate than what they would have been in the past over the region of interest. The *Temperature Changes* show that similar events produce temperatures in the present climate up to 2 °C warmer than what they would have been in the past, over a large area of the region analyzed. The *Precipitation Changes* show modest variations (up to 3 mm/day). *Windspeed Changes* indicate up to 4 km/h windier conditions over Northeast regions. We also note that *Similar Past Events* previously mainly occurred in June, while in the present climate they are mostly occurring in May. *Changes in Urban Areas* reveal that New York, Buffalo, and Washington are at least 1 °C warmer in the present compared to the past.

Finally, we find that sources of natural climate variability, mainly the Pacific Decadal Oscillation (PDO), influenced the event. This means that the changes we see in the event compared to the past may be primarily due to human driven climate change.

Conclusion

Based on the above, we conclude that heatwaves similar to the Eastern US heatwave are up to 2 °C warmer than the heatwaves previously observed in the country. We interpret the Eastern US heatwave as a somewhat uncommon event whose characteristics can mostly be ascribed to human driven climate change.

Additional Information : Complete Output of the Analysis

NB1: The following output is specifically intended for scientists and contain details that are fully understandable only by reading the methodology described in Faranda, D., Bourdin, S., Ginesta, M., Krouma, M., Noyelle, R., Pons, F., Yiou, P., and Messori, G.: A climate-change attribution retrospective of some impactful weather extremes of 2021, *Weather Clim. Dynam.*, 3, 1311–1340, <https://doi.org/10.5194/wcd-3-1311-2022>, 2022.

NB2: Colorscales may vary from the ClimaMeter figure presented above.

The figure shows the average of surface pressure anomaly (msl) (a), average 2-meter temperatures anomalies (t2m) (e), cumulated total precipitation (tp) (i), and average wind-speed (wspd) in the period of the event. Average of the surface pressure analogs found in the counterfactual [1979-2000] (b) and factual periods [2001-2022] (c), along with corresponding 2-meter temperatures (f, g),

cumulated precipitation (j, k), and wind speed (n, o). Changes between present and past analogues are presented for surface pressure Δslp (d), 2 meter temperatures Δt2m (h), total precipitation Δtp (i), and windspeed Δwspd (p): color-filled areas indicate significant anomalies with respect to the bootstrap procedure. Violin plots for past (blue) and present (orange) periods for Quality Q analogs (q), Predictability Index D (r), Persistence Index Θ (s), and distribution of analogs in each month (t). Violin plots for past (blue) and present (orange) periods for ENSO (u), AMO (v) and PDO (w). Number of the Analogues occurring in each subperiod (blue) and linear trend (black). Values for the peak day of the extreme event are marked by a blue dot. Horizontal bars in panels (q,r,s,u,v,w) correspond to the mean (black) and median (red) of the distributions.